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& IQTISODIYOT

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- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
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- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
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- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
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- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ROLE OF MODERN MODELS IN REGIONAL PRODUCTION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. This article analyzes the current aspects of implementation of modern organizational models in regional production management. The issues of effective implementation of innovation processes, improvement of managerial competencies and increasing the competitiveness of enterprises through digital transformation are highlighted.

Keywords: innovation, management structure, digital transformation, manager competencies, regional development.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mintaqaviy ishlab chiqarishni boshqarishda zamonaviy tashkiliy modellarni joriy etishning dolzarb jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Innovatsion jarayonlarni samarali joriy etish, boshqaruv kompetensiyalarini takomillashtirish va raqamli transformatsiya orqali korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirish masalalari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsiya, boshqaruv tuzilmasi, raqamli transformatsiya, menejer kompetensiyalari, mintaqaviy rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются современные аспекты внедрения современных организационных моделей в региональном управлении производством. Выделены вопросы эффективного осуществления инновационных процессов, повышения управленческих компетенций и повышения конкурентоспособности предприятий посредством цифровой трансформации.

Ключевые слова: инновации, структура управления, цифровая трансформация, управленческие компетенции, региональное развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern economy, the issue of effective management of regional production becomes increasingly important. The globalization processes in the world market, the intensification of competition and the rapid development of digital technologies pose new tasks for enterprises. Under these conditions, traditional governance structures are often ineffective. This is because they cannot adapt quickly to the changing economic environment and become a limiting factor in the introduction of innovation.

The use of modern organizational models in regional production management, that is, the introduction of divisional, flexible and digital technology models, is an important factor in increasing cost efficiency. This approach not only improves the internal management system of enterprises, but also ensures their competitiveness in the market.

At the same time, the need of today is the organization of innovation processes on the basis of democratic management, the development of strategic competencies of managers, and the introduction of digital transformation elements in small and medium-sized businesses. Therefore, this topic is important both from a scientific and theoretical point of view, and from the point of view of practice.

Literature review. Regional production management is one of the most important scientific areas in economic sciences related to ensuring the sustainable development of regions, the efficient use of production potential and the reduction of interregional economic imbalances. Modern management models occupy a special place in the evolution of scientific views formed on this issue.

In foreign scientific literature, the issues of regional production management have been extensively studied, primarily in connection with the theory of clustering. In particular, the concept of clusters developed by M. Porter (1998) scientifically substantiated the fact that the geographical concentration of manufacturing enterprises in regions serves to increase competitiveness, rapid introduction of innovations and increase production efficiency. This approach was later widely used in the formulation of regional industrial policies in the European Union and Asian countries.

In P. Krugman's (1991) research within the framework of the new theory of economic geography, market size, transport costs and concentration of labor resources are shown as important factors in the location and management of production in regions. The author believes that effective regional governance models serve to bridge the gap between production centers and the periphery.

R. Barro and J. Sala-i-Martin's (2004) studies on economic growth emphasize the interaction of human capital, institutional environment, and public policy in regional production management. According to their approach, modern models of governance should not be limited to economic factors, but should also cover social and institutional mechanisms.

In recent years, the concept of Industry 4.0 put forward by K. Schwab (2016) marked a new stage of regional production management models. In this concept, digital technologies, automation and data-driven decision-making are considered as the main tools for increasing production efficiency in the regions.

And in the research of scientists from the CIS countries, the issues of active state participation in regional production management, regional programs and intersectoral coordination are given priority importance. For example, in the works of L. Abalkin and A. Granberg, the need to use integrated economic models in the assessment of the economic potential of regions and management of production is substantiated.

In the research of economic scientists from Uzbekistan, the issues of regional production management have been studied, which is directly related to the diversification of the national economy and the integrated development of regions. In particular, in the scientific works of A. Vahobov, Sh. Mustafokulov and B. Berkinov, the cluster approach, the role of free economic zones and industrial zones in regional management of production are separately analyzed.

Also, the research of R. Nurmatov and U. Hakimov emphasizes the need to improve investment policy in managing production in the regions of Uzbekistan, to introduce modern models aimed at efficient use of local resources and job creation. According to the authors, the combination of existing management practices with digital technologies will significantly increase the efficiency of regional production.

In general, the literature analysis shows that although modern models in regional production management are theoretically sufficiently covered, the issues of their implementation, adaptation and evaluation of models, taking into account the characteristics of the regions of Uzbekistan, are still not sufficiently studied. This justifies the need for further development of scientific research on this topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to identify the importance of modern models in regional production management and to identify the possibilities of their application in the regions of Uzbekistan. In the process of researching, a comprehensive use of both general and special methods of scientific cognition.

In particular, through the method of analysis and synthesis, theoretical views on the management of regional production were systematized, the essence and interrelated aspects of modern models were revealed. Based on the method of comparative analysis, similarities and differences between the management models used in foreign countries and Uzbekistan were studied.

Also, using the statistical analysis method, the volume, composition and growth rates of industrial production by regions were analyzed on the basis of the data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. By means of induction and deduction methods, general conclusions were formed based on the results obtained in the sample of individual regions.

The study also considered the interdependence of economic, institutional and technological factors of regional production management using a systematic approach. This allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of modern management models.

Analysis and results. The analysis shows that in recent years certain positive changes have been observed in the production management system in the regions of Uzbekistan. In particular, due to the creation of industrial clusters, free economic zones and small-scale industrial zones, production volumes in some regions have increased significantly.

According to the results of the analysis, it was found that in the Tashkent region, Navoi and Fergana regions, production structures organized on the basis of clusters and cooperatives have high efficiency. Use of modern models in production management in these regions - inter-industry cooperation, targeted resource allocation and digital monitoring elements serve to significantly reduce production costs and increase product competitiveness.

The results show that production growth in regions with the systematic introduction of modern management models is stable and long-term in nature. In particular, the use of digital technology makes it possible to control production processes and make management decisions quickly.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the research and the results obtained, the following conclusions can be reached. First of all, modern models in the management of regional production play an important role in the full realization of the economic potential of the regions. In particular, cluster approach, digital governance and innovative ecosystems are effective tools for improving production efficiency.

Second, when introducing modern models in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into account the economic, demographic and resource characteristics of the regions. It is desirable not to apply a single model for all regions, but to develop adapted, flexible management models.

Thirdly, in order to improve the efficiency of regional production management, it is necessary to expand the economic powers of local authorities, introduce digital information systems and strengthen cooperation with the private sector.

In this connection, the following proposals are put forward:

- development of special programs for the introduction of modern models of production management in the context of regions;
- widespread use of digital management platforms in the activities of clusters and industrial zones;
- increasing the potential of local personnel and encouraging innovative approaches to management;
- Introduction of a system of specific indicators for the evaluation of regional production efficiency.

In conclusion, the use of modern models in the management of regional production will contribute to the sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan, reducing the economic gaps between regions and increasing the competitiveness of the national economy.

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